

PERSPECTIVES OF STAKEHOLDERS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SCHOOL FEEDING PROGRAMME AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates stakeholders' perspectives on the effectiveness of the School Feeding Programme (SFP) in Osun State, Nigeria. The objectives were to assess the programme's effectiveness, determine its impact on pupil enrollment, and examine pupils' and teachers' perceptions. A descriptive survey design was adopted by the researcher for this study. The study sample consisted 3,000 pupils and 300 teachers selected randomly from 60 public primary schools in the study areas. A structured questionnaire using a 4-point Likert scale was used for data collection. Instrument reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha (0.84). Results, analyzed using descriptive statistics, showed that the SFP improved pupils' enrollment rate, classroom attention, and school attendance. However, issues were raised regarding meal variety and supply consistency. Recommendations include improving nutritional quality, consistent funding, and active stakeholder feedback integration.

Introduction

Education is universally acknowledged as a powerful instrument for social and economic transformation. In Nigeria, as in many developing countries, significant efforts have been made to increase school enrolment rate, reduce dropout rates, and enhance the overall quality of primary school education. One initiative designed to support these objectives is the school feeding programme. (SFP). School feeding programmes as a social safety net, have been popular in developing as an instrument for achieving a Millennium Development Goals.

School – based feeding programmes (SBFPs) are intended to alleviate short hunger, improve nutrition and cognition of the children and transfer income to the families (Joma, 2012). Nigeria introduced the Home -Grown School Feeding Programme (HGSFP) in 2005, a pilot scheme, and it was later Integrated into the National Social Investment Programme {NSIP}| by Federal Government in 2016. The programme aims not only to improve pupils access to quality education but also to boost local agriculture and create job across the value chain -from smallholder farmers to cooks and food vendors

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(NSIP,2022) Osun state is notable as first Nigerian state to domesticate and implement the programme in 2006 through the Osun Elementary School Feeding and Health Programme (O- MEALS) .The programme target public primary school pupils ,especially those in lower primary classes with intention to improve children’s nutritional intake and cognitive development.

Since its inception in Osun State, the programme has undergone several phases of reform and evaluation. Despite the noble objectives, questions remain concerning its long-term sustainability, quality assurance, and impact on academic performance and community development. These questions are particularly important in light of persistent hindrances such as irregular funding, inconsistent food supply, poor monitoring, unqualified cooks and limited stakeholder engagement. However, despite over seven years of implementation, reports on the programme’s effectiveness are mixed. While government agencies report success, anecdotal evidence suggests issues such as inconsistency, food quality concerns, and poor stakeholder involvement. School feeding programmes (SFPs) have emerged as critical social intervention tools globally, aimed at improving educational outcomes, reducing hunger, and enhancing nutritional status among school-age children (Bundy et al., 2023 *Frontiers in Sustainable Food System*, 2024}.

In sub-Saharan Africa, where food insecurity and malnutrition remain persistent challenges, school feeding has been adopted not only as a means to support children's health and development but also as a strategic incentive to increase school enrollment, attendance, and

retention (World Food Programme,2022; UNICEF,2023]. Nigeria launched its National Home- Grown School Feeding Programme [NHGSFP] in 2016 as part of a broader social investment initiative. Osun State had pioneered this effort through the Osun Elementary School Feeding and Health programme[O-MEALS], a state lead initiative started in 2012. The programme aimed to provide free daily nutritious meals to public primary school pupils while simultaneously boosting local agriculture and resulted in creation of jobs within the community (Osun State Government, 2016)

Stakeholders comprising school administrators, teachers, parents, food vendors, government officials, and the pupils themselves play pivotal roles in shaping and sustaining the success of the programme. Their perspectives are crucial in evaluating the effectiveness of the SFP, as their experiences provide insight into the programme's reach, challenges, and impact. Understanding these viewpoints can inform policy improvements and ensure the sustainability and scalability of the programme. Previous research has highlighted both successes and shortcomings of school feeding interventions in Nigeria. While studies report increased school enrollment and improved child nutrition (Oyefade et al., 2020; Adedokun et al., 2018), concerns have also been raised about food quality, irregular funding, and lack of monitoring mechanisms (Abdullahi & Sulaiman, 2017). Hence, there is a compelling need to examine the programme through the lens of those directly involved. Thus, this study becomes necessary to understand the actual perceptions of those directly affected the pupils and teachers

and to evaluate whether the programme is truly achieving its objectives in Osun State.

Statement of the Problem

Although the school feeding programme has been widely commended for its potentials to enhance pupils' nutrition, attendance, and learning outcomes, its actual implementation in Osun State raised several issues regarding operational effectiveness, quality of meals, equity in distribution, and stakeholders' satisfaction. Despite its wide implementation and funding, there is inadequate empirical evidence assessing how the SFP impacts pupils' academic participation and performance in Osun State. Specifically, little is known about how pupils and teachers the primary stakeholders perceive its effectiveness. Without their input, policy decisions risk being disconnected from ground realities. This study addresses this gap.

Objectives of the Study

To investigate the effectiveness of the school feeding programme in Osun State.

To determine the impact of the school feeding programme on primary school pupils' enrollment in Osun State.

To find out the perception of pupils and teachers on the feeding programme in Osun State.

Research Questions

- 1 What is the level effectiveness of the school feeding programme in Osun State?
2. What impact does the school feeding programme have on primary school pupils enrollment in Osun State?
- 3 What are the perception of pupils and teachers regarding the effectiveness of the school feeding programme?

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design to obtain quantitative data on stakeholders' perspectives on the effectiveness of the School Feeding Programme among the primary school pupils in Osun State. The study sample consisted of a total of 3,000 pupils and 300 teachers were selected from 60 public primary schools using stratified and simple random sampling. Each school contributed 50 pupils and 5 teachers.

Research Instrument

A researcher-designed questionnaire titled Stakeholders' Perception of School Feeding Programme (SPSFP) was used for data collection. The instrument consisted of three sections aligned with the study objectives. Section A: Effectiveness of the School Feeding Programme (10 items). Section B: Impact on Enrollment (8 items) while Section C is on Perception of pupils and Teachers (10 items). Each item was rated using a 4-point.

Like scale:

- Strongly Agree (4)
- Agree (3)
- Disagree (2)

Reliability: The instrument was pilot-tested in three non-sampled schools. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was 0.84, indicating high reliability.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequency counts, mean scores, and standard deviations. Mean scores of 2.50 and above were considered as positive responses (agreement).

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Effectiveness of the School Feeding Programme

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Pupils are more attentive in class after meals	1450	900	400	250	3.18
Pupils arrive earlier due to free meals	1200	1000	500	300	3.03
Pupils are less likely to miss school	1300	1100	400	200	3.17

The findings show that stakeholders perceive the School Feeding Programme positively influencing pupils’ classroom attentiveness, punctuality, and attendance. The highest mean score (3.18) was recorded for pupils’ attentiveness in the classroom after meals. These results indicate that the nutritional benefit of school meals is directly linked to improve in concentration and learning readiness. This supports previous findings by Oyefade et al (2020), who similarly observed improvements in classroom engagement following meal provision. The mean score of 3.03 for pupils

arrive earlier due to free meals indicates that the programme serves as a stimulating factor for punctuality. This aligns with the argument by Bundy et al. (2023) that the school meals act as educational support and incentive for regular attendance. Also, the mean score 3.17 for reduced absenteeism suggests that the programme contributes to the sustainability of school attendance, which is consistent with UNICEF (2023) report showing that feeding programmes reduce dropout rates in low – income communities.

Table 2: Impact on Enrollment

Enrollment Trend	Average Pupils per School
Before SFP	350
After SFP	480

The data show a considerable increase of 130 pupils per school after the introduction of the SFP. This finding reinforces global evidence that the school feeding intervention can greatly boost enrolment (World Food Programme, 2022). The increase in the enrolment rate may be attributed

to factors like reduction in financial burden on the part of the parents, greater community awareness of benefits of the programme and attraction of pupils from surrounding communities due to free meals.

Table 3: Perception of Pupils and Teachers

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
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Meals are nutritious and balanced	800	1000	900	300	2.77
Meal quality is consistent	700	800	1000	500	2.57
Pupils enjoy the meals served	1600	900	300	200	3.30

The mean score of 2.77 for Meals are nutritious and balanced indicates a moderately positive perception, though there is room for improvement in nutritional variety and meal planning. The lowest score (2.57) for meal quality is consistent emphasizes a concern that directly affects programme credibility and pupils' satisfaction. This inconsistency could emerge from supply chain disruptions, irregular funding, or variations in vendor capacity, as also noted by Abdulahi & Sulaiman (2017). Interestingly, pupils enjoy the meals served recorded the highest mean (3.30) across this section, indicating that taste appeal remains a strength of the programme, which can positively influence school attendance and participation.

Conclusion

The study investigated stakeholders' perceptions on the effectiveness of school feeding programme among primary school pupils in Osun State. It was revealed that the programme has made notable contributions to improving pupils' attendance, reducing absenteeism, and increasing enrolment rate, especially in rural

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communities. However, the effectiveness of the programme is hindered by irregular food supply, poor quality of meals, inadequate supervision, and insufficient funding. Teachers, parents, and community members expressed mixed feelings while they acknowledge the benefit of the programme, they also emphasized the need for better coordination, coordination, consistent monitoring, and quality assurance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made

The government should establish a dedicated monitoring and evaluation framework to ensure transparency, consistency, and effectiveness in delivery of meals. Nutritionist and health experts should be involved in designing meal plans to meet the dietary needs of pupils. Adequate funding should be allocated and disbursed promptly to avoid interruptions in food supply. Delay payment to vendors often results in poor quality services delivery. Regular for cooks, vendors, and supervisors will enhance the quality-of-service delivery.

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